

Page # $n \ell m_\ell$	Static Radial Energy $\mathbf{KE}_r$ (Eqn. 7)	Polar Dynamic Orbiting Energy $\mathbf{KE}_\theta$ (Eqn. 8... note a $1/r^2$ in operator and r^2 associated with vol el)	Azimuthal Dynamic Orbiting Energy $\mathbf{KE}_\phi$ (Eqn. 9 ... note a $1/r^2$ in operator and r^2 associated with vol el)	Potential $\mathbf{V}_n$ (Eqn. 6)
# 2 1 0 0	$\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \left[R_{1,0}(r) \right] \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial R_{1,0}(r)}{\partial r} \right) \right] r^2 dr$ $\frac{\hbar^2}{2m a^2} = E_0$	NA	NA	$-e^2 \int_0^\infty C^2 R_{1,0}(r)^2 r dr$ Note: $(1/r)r^2 dr = r dr$
# 3 2 0 0	$\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \left[R_{2,0}(r) \right] \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial R_{2,0}(r)}{\partial r} \right) \right] r^2 dr$ E_0/n^2	NA	NA	$-e^2 \int_0^\infty C^2 R_{2,0}(r)^2 r dr$
# 4 2 1 0	$\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \left[R_{2,1}(r) \right] \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial R_{2,1}(r)}{\partial r} \right) \right] r^2 dr$ $E_0/3n^2$	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int \frac{1}{r^2} (r^2 e^{-r/a}) r^2 dr \cdot \frac{(\frac{3}{2}) \int_0^\pi \cos\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\cos\theta)) \right] \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi}{-2}$	NA	$-e^2 \int_0^\infty C^2 R_{2,1}(r)^2 r dr$
# 5 2 1 +/-1	“	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int \frac{1}{r^2} (r^2 e^{-r/a}) r^2 dr \cdot \frac{(\frac{3}{4}) \int_0^\pi \sin\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta)) \right] \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi}{-1/2}$	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \right) (r^2 e^{-r/a}) r^2 dr \cdot \frac{\frac{3}{4} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin\theta^2}{\sin\theta^2} \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-im_\ell\phi} \frac{\partial^2 e^{im_\ell\phi}}{\partial\phi^2} d\phi}{3/2 \quad -1}$	“
# 6 3 0 0	$\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \left[R_{3,0}(r) \right] \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial R_{3,0}(r)}{\partial r} \right) \right] r^2 dr$ E_0/n^2	NA	NA	$-e^2 \int_0^\infty C^2 R_{3,0}(r)^2 r dr$
# 7 3 1 0	$\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \left[R_{3,1}(r) \right] \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial R_{3,1}(r)}{\partial r} \right) \right] r^2 dr$ $5E_0/9n^2$	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \frac{R_{3,1}(r)^2}{r^2} r^2 dr \cdot \frac{\frac{3}{2} \int_0^\pi \cos\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\cos\theta)) \right] \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi}{-2}$	NA	$-e^2 \int_0^\infty C^2 R_{3,1}(r)^2 r dr$
# 8 3 1 +/-1	“	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \frac{R_{3,1}(r)^2}{r^2} r^2 dr \cdot \frac{\frac{3}{4} \int_0^\pi \sin\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta)) \right] \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi}{-1/2}$	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \frac{R_{3,1}(r)^2}{r^2} r^2 dr \cdot \frac{\frac{3}{4} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin\theta^2}{\sin\theta^2} \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-im_\ell\phi} \frac{\partial^2 e^{im_\ell\phi}}{\partial\phi^2} d\phi}{3/2 \quad -1}$	“
# 9 3 2 0	$\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \left[R_{3,2}(r) \right] \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial R_{3,2}(r)}{\partial r} \right) \right] r^2 dr$ $E_0/5n^2$	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int \frac{R_{3,2}(r)^2}{r^2} r^2 dr \cdot \frac{(\frac{5}{8}) \int_0^\pi (3\cos^2\theta - 1) \frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} \left[\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (3\cos^2\theta - 1) \right] \sin\theta d\theta}{-6}$	NA	$-e^2 \int_0^\infty C^2 R_{3,2}(r)^2 r dr$
# 10 3 2 +/-1	“	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \frac{R_{3,2}(r)^2}{r^2} r^2 dr \cdot \frac{(\frac{15}{4}) \int_0^\pi \sin\theta \cos\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta \cos\theta)) \right] \sin\theta d\theta}{-7/2}$	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \frac{R_{3,2}(r)^2}{r^2} r^2 dr \cdot \frac{\frac{15}{4} \int_0^\pi \frac{(\sin\theta \cos\theta)^2}{\sin\theta^2} \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-im_\ell\phi} \frac{\partial^2 e^{im_\ell\phi}}{\partial\phi^2} d\phi}{5/2 \quad -1}$	“
# 11 3 2 +/-2	“	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \frac{R_{3,2}(r)^2}{r^2} r^2 dr \cdot \frac{\frac{15}{16} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin\theta^2}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} \sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} (\sin\theta^2) \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi}{-1 \quad 1}$	$-\frac{\hbar^2 C^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty \frac{R_{3,2}(r)^2}{r^2} r^2 dr \cdot \frac{\frac{15}{16} \int_0^\pi \frac{(\sin\theta^2)^2}{\sin\theta^2} \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-im_\ell\phi} \frac{\partial^2 e^{im_\ell\phi}}{\partial\phi^2} d\phi}{5/4 \quad -4}$	“

Note: Normalized ϕ integrations for $\mathbf{KE}_\theta$ not displayed for 3 2 0 and 3 2 1 due to space limitation. Common non-operating radial terms are color coded. Common θ and ϕ operator integrations are background highlighted.

APPENDIX A1 1, 0, 0

$C^2 = 4/a^3, R(r) = e^{-r/a},$

$\Theta(\theta) = 1/2^{.5},$

$\mathcal{Y}(\varphi) = 1/(2\pi)^{.5}$

$a = \hbar^2 / me^2, E_0 = me^4 / 2\hbar^2.$

Radial (r) kinetic energy component KE_r (note angular components are normalized)

$$KE_r = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty e^{-r/a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} e^{-r/a} \right) \right] r^2 dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{4}{a^3} \right) \int_0^\infty \left(2r - \frac{r^2}{a} \right) e^{-2r/a} dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{4}{a^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) = E_0 \quad \boxed{KE_r = E_0} \quad A1(1)$$

Potential Energy V

$$V = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{r} e^{-2r/a} r^2 dr = -e^2 \left(\frac{4}{a^3} \right) \int_0^\infty r e^{-2r/a} dr = -e^2 \left(\frac{me^2}{\hbar^2} \right) = -2E_0 \quad \boxed{V = -2 E_0} \quad A1(2)$$

No other components like E_θ, E_φ

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

$$\int_0^\infty C^2 R(r)^2 r^2 dr = \frac{4}{a^3} \int_0^\infty e^{-2r/a} r^2 dr = \frac{4}{a^3} \left[\frac{2! a^3}{2^3} \right] = 1$$

Radial (r) kinetic energy component KE_r (note angular components are normalized)

$$KE_r = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C(2 - \frac{r}{a})e^{-r/2a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (C(2 - \frac{r}{a})e^{-r/2a}) \right] r^2 dr \quad A2(1)$$

$$= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty (2 - \frac{r}{a})e^{-r/2a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \left(-\frac{4r}{a} + \frac{5r^2}{2a^2} - \frac{r^3}{4a^3} \right) e^{-r/2a} \right] r^2 dr \quad A2(2)$$

$$= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{8a^3} \right) \int \left[-\frac{8r}{a} + \frac{9r^2}{a^2} - \frac{3r^3}{a^3} + \frac{r^4}{4a^4} \right] e^{-r/a} dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{8a^2} \right) [-2] = \frac{E_0}{n^2} \quad \boxed{KE_r = \frac{E_0}{n^2}} \quad A2(3)$$

Potential energy

$$V = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{r} (2 - \frac{r}{a})^2 e^{-r/a} r^2 dr = -e^2 \left(\frac{1}{8a^3} \right) \int_0^\infty (4r - \frac{4r^2}{a} + \frac{r^3}{a^2}) e^{-r/a} dr = -\frac{e^2}{8} \left(\frac{me^2}{\hbar^2} \right) = -\frac{2}{n^2} E_0 \quad \boxed{V = -\frac{2}{n^2} E_0} \quad A2(4)$$

No other components like E_θ, E_φ

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

$$\int_0^\infty C^2 R(r)^2 r^2 dr = \frac{4}{8a^3} \int_0^\infty (1 - \frac{r}{2a})^2 e^{-r/a} r^2 dr = \frac{1}{2a^3} \int_0^\infty \left[1 - \frac{r}{a} + \frac{r^2}{4a^2} \right] e^{-r/a} r^2 dr$$

$$= \frac{1}{2a^3} [2!a^3 - \frac{1}{a} 3!a^4 + \frac{4!}{4a^2} a^5] = 1$$

$$C^2 = 1/24a^5,$$

$$R(r) = re^{-r/2a},$$

$$\Theta(\theta) = (3/2)^{-5} \cos\theta,$$

$$\mathcal{Y}(\phi) = 1/(2\pi)^{.5}$$

$$a = \hbar^2 / me^2, E_0 = me^4/2\hbar^2.$$

Radial (r) kinetic energy (Eqn. 7) component $\mathbf{KE}_r$ (note angular components are normalized)

$$\mathbf{KE}_r = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty r e^{-r/2a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} r e^{-r/2a} \right) \right] r^2 dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{24a^5} \right) \int_0^\infty \left(2r^2 - \frac{2r^3}{a} + \frac{r^4}{4a^2} \right) e^{-r/a} dr = \frac{E_0}{3n^2} \quad \boxed{\mathbf{KE}_r = \frac{E}{3n^2}} \quad \text{A3(1)}$$

Polar kinetic energy $\mathbf{KE}_\theta$, (Eqn. 8) with radial part of the problem analyzed first. Note $1/r^2$ associated with the θ operator

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int \frac{1}{r^2} (r^2 e^{-r/a}) r^2 dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{12a^2} \right) \quad \text{A3(2)}$$

The angular part of the problem

$$\underbrace{\left(\frac{3}{2} \right) \int_0^\pi \cos\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\cos\theta)) \right] \sin\theta d\theta}_{-2} \cdot \underbrace{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi}_1 \quad \text{A3(3)}$$

$$\mathbf{KE}_\theta = \text{A3(2)} \times \text{A3(3)}$$

$$\boxed{\mathbf{KE}_\theta = \frac{2}{3n^2} E_0} \quad \text{A3(4)}$$

Potential Energy V

$$V = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{r} (r^2 e^{-r/a}) r^2 dr = -\frac{e^2}{24a^5} (3!a^4) = -\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{me^4}{\hbar^2} \right) = -\frac{2}{n^2} E_0 \quad \boxed{V = -\frac{2}{n^2} E_0} \quad \text{A3(5)}$$

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

$$\frac{1}{24a^5} \int_0^\infty r^2 e^{-r/a} r^2 dr = \frac{1}{24a^5} 4!a^5 = 1$$

Radial (r) KE_r kinetic energy (Eqn. 7) (angular parts normalized). Same result as for 2, 1, 0

$$= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C r e^{-r/2a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (C e^{-r/2a})) \right] r^2 dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left[2r^2 - \frac{2}{a} r^3 + \frac{r^4}{4a^2} \right] e^{-r/a} dr \quad A4(1)$$

$$= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{24a^5} \right) (2! \cdot a^3 - 2 \cdot 3! a^4 + \frac{4!}{4a^2}) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{24a^2} \right) (-2) \rightarrow \boxed{KE_r = \frac{E_o}{3n^2}} \quad A4(2)$$

Polar (θ) KE_θ Kinetic energy (Eqn. 8) component. The radial part of the integration yields...

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \right) (r e^{-r/2a})^2 r^2 dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{24a^5} \right) \int_0^\infty r^2 e^{-r/a} dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{12a^2} \right) \quad A4(3)$$

The polar integration yields with the azimuth normalized yields

$$\left(\frac{3}{4} \right) \int_0^\pi \sin\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\sin\theta)) \right] \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \right) \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi = \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) \int_0^\pi (\cos\theta^2 \sin\theta - \sin\theta^3) d\theta = -\frac{1}{2} \quad A4(4)$$

The polar contribution to the kinetic energy is then A4(3) x A4(4), ie

$$\boxed{KE_\theta = \frac{E_o}{6n^2}} \quad A4(5)$$

Azimuthal (φ) KE_φ kinetic energy (Eqn. 9) component with polar normalized

Radial part of the integration is the same as used for determining E_θ. The angular part is shown below

$$\frac{3}{4} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin\theta^2}{\sin\theta^2} \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-im_\ell \phi} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} e^{im_\ell \phi} d\phi = -\frac{3}{2} \quad A4(6)$$

The azimuthal contribution is A4(3) x A4(6), ie

$$\boxed{KE_\phi = \frac{E_o}{2n^2}} \quad A4(7)$$

$$\text{Potential } V = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right)^2 e^{-2r/3a} r^2 dr = -\left(\frac{32e^2}{3^7 a^3} \right) \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r^3}{a^2} - \frac{r^4}{3a^3} + \frac{r^5}{36a^4} \right) e^{-2r/3a} dr = -\frac{e^2}{9a} = -\frac{2E_o}{n^2} \quad A(8)$$

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

Same as for 2, 1, 0

Radial (r) kinetic energy (Eqn. 7) component $\mathbf{KE}_r$ (note angular components are normalized)

$$\mathbf{KE}_r = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C(1 - \frac{2r}{3a} + \frac{2r^2}{27a^2}) e^{-r/3a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (C(1 - \frac{2r}{3a} + \frac{2r^2}{27a^2}) e^{-r/3a}) \right] r^2 dr \quad \text{A5(1)}$$

$$= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C(1 - \frac{2r}{3a} + \frac{2r^2}{27a^2}) e^{-r/3a} \left[-\frac{2r}{a} + \frac{13r^2}{9a^2} - \frac{18r^3}{81a^3} + \frac{2r^4}{81.3a^4} \right] e^{-r/3a} r^2 dr \quad \text{A5(2)}$$

$$= \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{4}{27a^3} \right) \int_0^\infty \left[-\frac{2r}{a} + \frac{25r^2}{9a^2} - \frac{36r^3}{3^3 a^3} + \frac{64r^4}{3^5 a^4} - \frac{16r^5}{3^6 a^5} + \frac{4r^6}{3^8 a^6} \right] e^{-2r/3a} dr \quad \text{A5(3)}$$

$$= \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{4}{27a^3} \right) \left[\frac{-2.1! a^2 3^2}{a.2^2} + \frac{25.2! a^3 3^3}{9a^2.2^3} - \frac{36.3! 3^4 a^4}{3^3 a^3.2^4} + \frac{64.4! 3^5 a^5}{3^5 a^4.2^5} - \frac{16.5! 3^6 a^6}{3^6 a^5.2^6} + \frac{4.6! 3^7 a^7}{81^2. a^6.2^7} \right] \quad \text{A5(4)}$$

$$= \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{4}{27a^2} \right) \left[-\frac{9}{2} + \frac{75}{4} - \frac{81}{2} + 48 - 30 + \frac{15}{2} \right] = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{4}{27} \right) \frac{m e^4}{\hbar^2} \left(\frac{-3}{4} \right) = \boxed{\frac{E_o}{n^2}} \quad \text{A5(5)}$$

Potential Energy V similar to A2(3) except $-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}$ is replaced by $-e^2$ and integrand $1/r$ term partly cancels r^2 in vol element

$$V = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \left[r - \frac{4r^2}{3a} + \frac{16r^3}{27a^2} - \frac{8r^4}{3^4 a^3} + \frac{4r^5}{3^6 a^4} \right] e^{-2r/3a} dr = -\frac{e^2}{9a} \boxed{= -\frac{2E_o}{n^2}} \quad \text{A5(6)}$$

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{4}{27a^3} \right) \int \left(1 - \frac{4r}{3a} + \frac{16r^2}{27a^2} - \frac{8r^3}{81a^3} + \frac{4r^4}{81a^4} \right) e^{-2r/3a} r^2 dr \\ & \left(\frac{4}{27a^3} \right) \left[2! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^3 - \frac{4}{3a} 3! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^4 + \frac{16}{27a^2} \cdot 4! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^5 - \frac{8}{81a^3} 5! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^6 + \frac{4}{3^6 a^4} 6! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^7 \right] \\ & = 4 \left[\frac{1}{4} - \frac{3}{2} + 4 - 5 + \frac{5}{2} \right] = 1 \end{aligned}$$

Radial (r) kinetic energy (Eqn. 7) component $\mathbf{KE}_r$ (note angular components are normalized)

$$\mathbf{KE}_r = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) e^{-r/3a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(C \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) e^{-r/3a} \right) \right) \right] r^2 dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) \left[\frac{2r}{a} - \frac{7r^2}{3a^2} + \frac{4r^3}{9a^3} - \frac{r^4}{54a^4} \right] e^{-2r/3a} dr \quad \text{A6(1)}$$

$$= \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left[\frac{2r^2}{a^2} - \frac{8r^3}{3a^3} + \frac{5r^4}{6a^4} - \frac{5r^5}{54a^5} + \frac{r^6}{6.54a^6} \right] e^{-2r/3a} dr = \frac{5}{3^4 a^2} \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} = \frac{5E_0}{9n^2} \quad \mathbf{KE}_r = \frac{5E_0}{9n^2} \quad \text{A6(2)}$$

Polar (θ) kinetic energy (Eqn. 8) component $\mathbf{KE}_\theta$. Noting r^2 in vol el./cancels with r^2 in operator, radial part yields...

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right)^2 e^{-2r/3a} dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r^2}{a^2} - \frac{r^3}{3a^3} + \frac{r^4}{36a^4} \right) e^{-2r/3a} dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{3^4 m a^4} = -\frac{2}{9n^2} \left(\frac{m e^4}{2\hbar^2} \right) \quad \text{A6(3)}$$

The separated polar and azimuthal contribution is . . .

$$\left(\frac{3}{2} \right) \int_0^\pi \cos\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\cos\theta) \right) \right] \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi = \left(\frac{3}{2} \right) \int_0^\pi -2\cos\theta^2 \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi = -2 \quad \text{A6(4)}$$

The polar contribution to the kinetic energy is then A6(3) x A6(4), ie $\rightarrow$

$$\mathbf{KE}_\theta = \frac{4E_0}{9n^2} \quad \text{A6(5)}$$

Azimuthal (ϕ) kinetic energy component $\mathbf{KE}_\phi$ none

Potential Energy V note 1/r term partly cancels with r^2 in volume element

$$\mathbf{V} = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r^3}{a^2} - \frac{r^4}{3a^3} + \frac{r^5}{36a^4} \right) e^{-2r/3a} dr = -e^2 \left(\frac{32}{3^7 a^3} \right) \left(\frac{3! \cdot 3^4 a^4}{2^4 a^2} - \frac{4! \cdot 3^5 a^5}{2^5 \cdot 3 a^3} + \frac{5! \cdot 3}{2^6 \cdot 36 a^4} \right) = -\frac{e^2}{9a} = -\frac{2me^4}{18\hbar^2} = -2 \frac{E_0}{n^2} \quad \mathbf{V} = -2 \frac{E_0}{n^2} \quad \text{A6(6)}$$

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

$$\frac{32}{3^7 a^3} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r^4}{a^2} - \frac{r^5}{3a^3} + \frac{r^6}{36a^4} \right) e^{-2r/3a} dr$$

$$\frac{32}{3^7 a^3} \left[\frac{4!}{a^2} \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^5 - \frac{5!}{3a^3} \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^6 + \frac{6!}{36a^4} \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^7 \right] = 1$$

Radial (r) kinetic energy (Eqn. 7) component $\mathbf{KE}_r$ (note angular components are normalized). Same as for 3 1 0

$$\mathbf{KE}_r = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) e^{-r/3a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(C \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) e^{-r/3a} \right) \right) \right] r^2 dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) \left[\frac{2r}{a} - \frac{7r^2}{3a^2} + \frac{4r^3}{9a^3} - \frac{r^4}{54a^4} \right] e^{-2r/3a} dr \quad \text{A7(1)}$$

$$= \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left[\frac{2r^2}{a^2} - \frac{8r^3}{3a^3} + \frac{5r^4}{6a^4} - \frac{5r^5}{54a^5} + \frac{r^6}{6.54a^6} \right] e^{-2r/3a} dr \quad \text{A7(2)}$$

$$= \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{32}{3^7 a^3} \right) \left[\frac{2}{a^2} 2! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^3 - \frac{8}{3a^3} 3! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^4 + \frac{5}{6a^4} 4! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^5 - \frac{5}{54a^5} 5! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^6 + \frac{1}{6.54a^6} 6! \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^7 \right] = \frac{5}{3^4 a^2} \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \rightarrow \boxed{\mathbf{KE}_r = \frac{5E_0}{9n^2}} \quad \text{A7(3)}$$

Polar (θ) kinetic energy (Eqn. 8) component $\mathbf{KE}_\theta$. Noting r^2 in vol el./cancels with r^2 in operator, radial part yields...

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right)^2 e^{-2r/3a} dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r^2}{a^2} - \frac{r^3}{3a^3} + \frac{r^4}{36a^4} \right) e^{-2r/3a} dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{3^4 m a^4} = -\frac{2}{9n^2} \left(\frac{m e^4}{2\hbar^2} \right) \quad \text{A7(4)}$$

$$\left(\frac{3}{4} \right) \int_0^\pi \sin\theta \left[\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\sin\theta) \right) \right] \sin\theta d\theta \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \right) \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi = \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) \int_0^\pi (\cos\theta^2 \sin\theta - \sin\theta^3) d\theta = -\frac{1}{2} \quad \text{(Same } Y_{lm} \text{ as in 2, 1, +/-1 case)} \quad \text{A7(5)}$$

The polar contribution to the kinetic energy is then A7(4) x A7(5), ie $\rightarrow$

$$\boxed{\mathbf{KE}_\theta = \frac{E_0}{9n^2}} \quad \text{A7(6)}$$

Azimuthal (φ) kinetic energy (Eqn. 9) component $\mathbf{KE}_\varphi$. The angular part is shown below. Radial part same as for E_0 .

$$\frac{3}{4} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin\theta^2}{\sin\theta^2} \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-im_\ell \phi} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} e^{im_\ell \phi} d\phi = -\frac{3}{2} \quad \text{A7(7)}$$

The azimuthal contribution to the kinetic energy is then A7(4) x A7(7), ie $\rightarrow$

$$\boxed{\mathbf{KE}_\phi = \frac{3E_0}{9n^2}} \quad \text{A7(8)}$$

Potential energy V (Eqn. 6) ($2 r^2$ terms cancel)

$$\mathbf{V} = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r^3}{a^2} - \frac{r^4}{3a^3} + \frac{r^5}{36a^4} \right) e^{-2r/3a} dr = -e^2 \left(\frac{32}{3^7 a^3} \right) \left(\frac{3! \cdot 3^4 a^4}{2^4 a^2} - \frac{4! \cdot 3^5 a^5}{2^5 \cdot 3 a^3} + \frac{5! \cdot 3}{2^6 \cdot 36 a^4} \right) = -\frac{e^2}{9a} = -\frac{2me^4}{18\hbar^2} = -2 \frac{E_0}{n^2} \quad \boxed{\mathbf{V} = -2 \frac{E_0}{n^2}} \quad \text{A7(9)}$$

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK same as for 3 1 0

Radial (r) kinetic energy (Eqn. 7) component $\mathbf{KE}_r$

$$\mathbf{KE}_r = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty r^2 e^{-r/3a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (C r^2 e^{-r/3a}) \right) \right] r^2 dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C^2 \left(6r^2 - \frac{2r^3}{a} + \frac{r^4}{9a^2} \right) r^2 e^{-2r/3a} dr \quad \text{A8(1)}$$

$$= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \left(\frac{6 \cdot 4! \cdot 3^5}{2^5} - \frac{2 \cdot 5! \cdot 3^6}{2^6} + \frac{6! \cdot 3^7}{9 \cdot 2^7} \right) a^5 = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{8 \cdot 3^7}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{5}{4} + \frac{5}{8} \right)$$

$$\mathbf{KE}_r = \frac{1E_0}{5n^2} \quad \text{A8(2)}$$

Note that the angular parts of this component are normalized

Polar (θ) kinetic energy (Eqn. 8) component $\mathbf{KE}_\theta$. The radial part of the integration yields...

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int C^2 r^4 e^{-2r/3a} dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \right) \left(\frac{4! \cdot 3^5 a^5}{2^5} \right) = -\frac{2}{15} \frac{1}{n^2} \frac{me^4}{2\hbar^2} = -\frac{2}{15} \frac{E_0}{n^2} \quad \text{A8(3)}$$

The separated polar contribution is ...

$$\left(\frac{5}{8} \right) \int_0^\pi (3\cos\theta^2 - 1) \frac{1}{r^2 \sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left[\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (3\cos\theta^2 - 1) \right] r^2 \sin\theta d\theta = \frac{30}{8} \int_0^\pi (6\cos\theta^2 - 9\cos\theta^4 - 1) \sin\theta d\theta = -6 \quad \text{A8(4)}$$

The polar contribution to the kinetic energy is then A8(3) x A8(4) $\rightarrow$

$$\mathbf{KE}_\theta = \frac{4E_0}{5n^2} \quad \text{A8(5)}$$

Potential energy V (Eqn. 6)

$$\mathbf{V} = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{r} r^4 e^{-2r/3a} r^2 dr = -e^2 \left(\frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \right) \left(\frac{5! \cdot 3^6 a^6}{2^6} \right) = -\frac{2E_0}{n^2}$$

$$\mathbf{V} = -\frac{2E_0}{n^2} \quad \text{A8(6)}$$

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

$$\mathbf{KE}_r = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) e^{-r/3a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(C \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) e^{-r/3a} \right) \right) \right] r^2 dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} C^2 \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{r}{a} - \frac{r^2}{6a^2} \right) \left[\frac{2r}{a} - \frac{7r^2}{3a^2} + \frac{4r^3}{9a^3} - \frac{r}{54a^4} \right] e^{-2r/3a} dr = \frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 \cdot a^7} \int_0^\infty r^6 e^{-2r/3a} dr = \frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 \cdot a^7} (6.5.4.3.2) \left(\frac{3a}{2} \right)^7 = 1$$

Radial (r) kinetic energy KE_r (Eqn. 7) (the angular parts of this contribution are normalized. Same for 3,2,1 and 3,2,0)

$$KE_r = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty r^2 e^{-r/3a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (C r^2 e^{-r/3a}) \right) \right] r^2 dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C^2 \left(6r^2 - \frac{2r^3}{a} + \frac{r^4}{9a^2} \right) r^2 e^{-2r/3a} dr \quad A9(1)$$

$$= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \left(\frac{6 \cdot 4! 3^5}{2^5} - \frac{2 \cdot 5! 3^6}{2^6} + \frac{6! 3^7}{9 \cdot 2^7} \right) a^5 = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{5}{4} + \frac{5}{8} \right) \quad \boxed{KE_r = \frac{3E_0}{15n^2}} \quad A9(2)$$

Polar (θ) kinetic energy KE_θ (Eqn. 8) Radial part, noting cancellation of operator $1/r^2$ with r^2 vol element

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int C^2 r^4 e^{-2r/3a} dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \right) \left(\frac{4! 3^5 a^5}{2^5} \right) = -\frac{2}{15n^2} \frac{me^4}{2\hbar^2} \quad A9(3)$$

The separated polar contribution is . . .

$$\left(\frac{15}{4} \right) \int_0^\pi \sin\theta \cos\theta \left[\frac{1}{r^2 \sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\sin\theta \cos\theta) \right) \right] r^2 \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi = \left(\frac{15}{4} \right) \int_0^\pi \sin\theta \cos\theta (6\cos^3\theta - 5\cos\theta) d\theta = \frac{-7}{2} \quad A9(4)$$

The polar contribution to the kinetic energy is then A9(3) x A9(4) $\rightarrow$

$$\boxed{KE_r = \frac{7E_0}{15n^2}} \quad A9(5)$$

Azimuth KE_ϕ kinetic energy (Eqn. 9) angular factor

$$\frac{15}{4} \int_0^\pi \frac{(\sin\theta \cos\theta)^2}{\sin\theta} \sin\theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-im_\ell \phi} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} e^{im_\ell \phi} d\phi = \frac{15}{4} \int_0^\pi \cos^2\theta \sin\theta d\theta \cdot 1 = \frac{-5}{2} \quad A9(6)$$

Azimuth KE_ϕ contribution is then A9(3) x A9(6)

$$\boxed{KE_\phi = \frac{5}{15n^2} \frac{me^4}{2\hbar^2}} \quad A9(7)$$

Potential energy V (Eqn. 6)

$$V = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{r} r^4 e^{-2r/3a} r^2 dr = -e^2 \left(\frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \right) \left(\frac{5! 3^6 a^6}{2^6} \right) = -\frac{2E_0}{n^2} \quad \boxed{V = -\frac{2E_0}{n^2}} \quad A9(8)$$

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

Same as for 3, 2, 0

Kinetic energy KE_r (Eqn. 7) (the angular parts of this contribution are normalized)

$$KE_r = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty r^2 e^{-r/3a} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (C r^2 e^{-r/3a}) \right) \right] r^2 dr = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int_0^\infty C^2 \left(6r^2 - \frac{2r^3}{a} + \frac{r^4}{9a^2} \right) r^2 e^{-2r/3a} dr \quad A10(1)$$

$$= -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \left(\frac{6 \cdot 4! \cdot 3^5}{2^5} - \frac{2 \cdot 5! \cdot 3^6}{2^6} + \frac{6! \cdot 3^7}{9 \cdot 2^7} \right) a^5 = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{5}{4} + \frac{5}{8} \right) \quad \boxed{KE_r = \frac{3E_0}{15n^2}} \quad A10(2)$$

Polar (θ) kinetic energy KE_θ . (Eqn. 8) Radial part, noting cancellation of operator $1/r^2$ with r^2 vol element

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int C^2 r^4 e^{-2r/3a} dr = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \right) \left(\frac{4! \cdot 3^5 a^5}{2^5} \right) = -\frac{2}{15n^2} \frac{me^4}{2\hbar^2} = -\frac{2E_0}{15n^2} \quad A10(3)$$

The separated polar contribution is . . .

$$\frac{15}{16} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left[\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \sin^2 \theta \right] \sin \theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi = \frac{15}{8} \int_0^\pi (2\sin^3 \theta - 3\sin^5 \theta) d\theta \cdot 1 = -1 \quad A10(4)$$

The polar contribution to the kinetic energy is then A10(3) x A10(4) $\rightarrow$

$$\boxed{KE_r = \frac{2E_0}{15n^2}} \quad A10(5)$$

Azimuthal (φ) factor is

$$\frac{15}{16} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{\sin^2 \theta} \sin \theta d\theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{-im_l \phi} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} e^{im_l \phi} d\phi \quad A10(6)$$

Azimuth KE_ϕ contribution is then A10(3) x A10(6)

$$\boxed{KE_\phi = \frac{10}{15n^2} \frac{me^4}{2\hbar^2}} \quad A10(7)$$

Potential energy V (Eqn. 6)

$$V = -e^2 C^2 \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{r} r^4 e^{-2r/3a} r^2 dr = -e^2 \left(\frac{8}{5 \cdot 3^9 a^7} \right) \left(\frac{5! \cdot 3^6 a^6}{2^6} \right) = -\frac{2E_0}{n^2} \quad \boxed{V = -\frac{2E_0}{n^2}} \quad A10(8)$$

RADIAL NORMALIZATION CHECK

Same as for 3, 2, 0